

PROPOSING AUTOMATED REGRESSION SUITE USING OPEN SOURCE TOOLS FOR A HEALTH CARE SOLUTION

Anjali Rawat and Shahid Ali

Department of Information Technology, AGI Institute, Auckland, New Zealand

ABSTRACT

Regression testing is very important for the delivery of high quality product. It helps to simulate a suite of critical test cases periodically and helps to identify if introduction of any new features or any source code change has adversely affected the software quality or functionality. As a result, regression testing cannot be ignored from the software testing life cycle (STLC). But just doing a regression testing cannot be beneficial until it is accompanied by automation testing. Automated regression suite not only saves time and cost by re-running test scripts again and again but it also provide the confidence that all the critical test cases has been covered, providing more confidence in the quality of the product and increasing the ability to meet schedules. IT has an ability to explore the whole software every day without requiring much of manual effort. Current software is going through continuous development which requires testing again and again to check if new feature implementation has affected the existing functionality. In addition to this, it is facing issue in validation of the installation at client site and requires availability of testers to check the critical functionality of the software manually. This paper came up with the solution of creating automated regression suite for the software. The current research will provide guidelines to the future researchers on how to create an automated regression suite for any web application using open source tools.

KEYWORDS

Automation testing, Regression testing, Visual Studio, C#, Selenium Webdriver, Agile- Scrum Methodology, Health care solution, Visual SVN, Trello

1. INTRODUCTION

The Company was founded in 2002 and is a leading healthcare software consultancy offering real knowledge and experience of the medical field to shape solutions for diverse industry requirements. It creates software solutions for health monitoring environments. This company specialize in systems across 3 markets:

- Rehabilitation
- Community Health
- Occupational Health

The Company is currently developing an Occupational Health Management Solution (OHMS), a cloud-based occupational health platform designed to help organizations proactively manage employee health monitoring, pre-employment and wellbeing activities. This solution is built around Electronic Health Record (EHR). An EHR is a person-centric dataset which provides a 360 degree view of an individual's health and well-being, as well as relevant clinical episode of care. It has an ability to capture and manage information such as patient demographics, progress notes, medications, past medical history, immunizations and laboratory tests. OHMS is going through continuous development to meet the requirements of multiple clients and therefore

requires testing of software again and again to check if new feature implementation has affected the existing functionality of the software. Currently to confirm that OHMS has been installed correctly at client site, tester are send to client's premises and test the critical functionality of the software manually. Both these activities need lot of time and manual efforts and therefore this paper has tried to suggest creation of automated regression suite for OHMS. This suite can be executed at client site for checking the functionality of the software. In addition to this, this suite will also help the testing team to validate if the new features which have been added to the existing software are affecting the existing system or not.

The scope of this project is to create automated regression test suite. This research project report is organized as follow: Section 2 focuses on the literature review of various studies concentrating on automation regression. Section 3 is focused on the research methodology for this research project. Section 4 of this research is focused on project execution results. Discussion to results of this project is provided in section 5. Section 6 is dedicated towards the future work recommendations. Finally, in section 7 conclusions to the research is provided.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A thorough study of different research paper has been done before implementing any methodology or technique for this project. Regression testing has a capability to detect the bugs caused by software enhancement or bug fix [1]. Evidences regarding advantage of implementing automation testing which includes saving time by re-running test scripts again and again, providing more confidence in the quality of the product, increasing the ability to meet schedules and significantly reducing the manual efforts of the testers are provided on the basis of survey of 115 software professionals [2]. In addition to this, automated regression suite has an ability to explore the whole software every day without requiring much of manual effort. Also, bug identification is easier after the incorrect changes have been made [3].

Selenium is one of the most popular open source tools for web based testing and supports all prominent browsers and operating systems. It supports automation of dynamic web pages where web elements changes without the page being reloaded [4]. The selection of selenium Webdriver can be further supported by highlighting the easiness of test suite maintenance using selenium Webdriver [9]. Creation of automation framework for web application with "Selenium Webdriver could reduce time for development, increase the return on investments (ROI) and minimize the risk" (Elior, 2017).

Visual studio (VS) is a fully-featured integrated development environment (IDE) for Android, iOS, Windows, web, and cloud which is freely available. It supports GitHub. Its functionality and features can be extended through plug-ins. Number of extensions can be found in the Visual Studio Gallery for VS [6]. Trello is a free cloud-based project management tool which gives an overview of what is being worked on and who is working on a particular task. It helps project leaders in managing large projects, planning programs, and coordinating teams [7].

Scrum methodology is ideal for the software where client requirements are rapidly changing. It emphasis on incremental development effort which allows early delivery of a portion of the solution without the entire solution to be 100% complete and hence helps to gain client confidence over the team. Work estimates are much easier under this methodology [8].

Most of these research papers are confined to the usage of JAVA as the programming language in their projects, whereas, a large portion of companies in New Zealand still uses C# as a

programming language in their coding. This report has explained how automation can be achieved using C# with selenium Webdriver. In addition, this paper has explained how the combination of selenium Webdriver with Visual Studio can help any organization to achieve regression automation.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology for OHMS Project has been discussed below.

4.1 Proposed Architecture for the project

Proposed architecture for OHMS Project is shown in Figure 1. The whole suite has been divided into three folder structure. The first folder named as Initial Execution is having a main class in it. This main class will initialize the scripts for execution. Second folder named as Task Execution has a Base class inside it which again have two abstract methods namely up and down methods for creating and deleting entries respectively and the third folder named as Test Scripts have all the scripts which contain the web elements and the actions which are getting performed on the OHMS.

Main class calls “Browser start” class, which helps to initialize the Webdriver and later return the initialized Webdriver to the main class. Classes defined under Test Scripts folder inherit and implement the base class. Once these two actions are complete, main class start calling test script’s classes one by one, to perform the actions on the OHMS and displays the results in the console for each action.

Figure 1. Proposed Architecture for OHMS Project

3.2 Project Execution

3.2.1 Testing Phases for Project

Automation testing phase which has been implemented by OHMS project is shown in figure 2. It shows the different phases involved in the whole testing process along with the different activities which have been performed in each stage. This project has 6 phases. In first phases requirements are gathered from the client and a technical analysis of those requirements is done. In this Company, it needs the involvement of Business Analyst (BA) and product owner (PO) for the accomplishment of this task. Second phase involves test planning including creation of test strategy and test plan documents. PO will help the scrum team in identifying the user stories and will also prioritize the user stories which need to be covered in each sprint. In Third phase environment is set up. During this phase, Visual Studio has been installed in the local machine, Selenium Webdriver related jar files and libraries has been imported and Visual SVN is installed which helped the team to commit the updated code to the central repository. Once the setup was ready, team starts designing test scripts on the basis of Acceptance criteria mentioned on the user stories. Traceability matrix is used to make sure that all the requirements have been covered by the test scripts. In the execution phase, test scripts are executed and once they are passed they are committed to the central repository. The last phase was the test result analysis phase where the complete code and the output was reviewed by the scrum team, and team members would suggest areas of improvement.

Figure 2. Testing Phases for OHMS project

3.2.2 Test Cases

Test cases are the set of steps and conditions which helps to determine whether application under test works correctly and meets the requirements. Some of the test cases which have been created for OHMS are shown in Table 1. This table explains what each test case is supposed to do, pre-requisites which need to be fulfilled, detailed steps which need to be followed to achieve the expected result. Test cases are helpful in ensuring that all the requirements have been covered and creates a layout for the automation scripts.

Test Case ID	Test Case Description	Pre-requisites	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
TC_001	As an Admin, I should be able to login to OHMS using valid credentials	URL : OHMS website Username : "Admin" Password : "XXXXXX"	1.Navigate to "OHMS website" 2.Enter username 3.Enter Password 4.Click on Login	User should be logged-In to OHMS successfully	User is successfully logged-in	PASS
TC_002	As an Admin, I should be able to create person for Program manager (PM) role	Logged-In as Company Admin	1.Navigate to "My Company" tab 2.Go to "People" tab 3.Click New 4.Fill details 5. Create	A person should get created for home company	Person is successfully created	PASS
TC_003	As an Admin, I should be able to assign PM role and valid credentials to newly created person	Logged in as Company Admin	1. Navigate to "Security" tab 2.Enter password 3.Click on "Program Manager" role 4. Create	"Program Manager" role should be assigned to newly created person successfully.	"Program Manager" role is assigned successfully	PASS

TC_004	As an Admin, I should be able to logout as Company's Admin	Logged in as Company Admin	1. Navigate to "Menu" 2. Click on "Sign-Out"	User should be logged-Out successfully	User is successfully logged-Out	PASS
TC_005	As a PM, I should be able to login to OHMS	URL : OHMS website Username : "PM HomeCompany" Password : "XXXXXX"	1.Navigate to "OHMS website" 2.Enter username 3.Enter Password 4.Click on Login	PM should be logged-In to OHMS successfully	PM is successfully logged in	PASS
TC_006	As a PM, I should be able to create Client company	Logged in as PM	1. Click on "Client Company" tab 2.Click on "New" 3. Fill details 4.Click on "Create"	Client Company should be created successfully	Client Company is created successfully	PASS
TC_007	As a PM, I should be able to create Client company Sites	Logged in as PM	1. Click on newly created "Client Company" 2. Click on "New" 3. Click on "New Site" 4.Fill details 5.Click on "Create"	Sites should be created successfully	Sites are created successfully	PASS
TC_008	As a PM, I should be able to create Client company Division	Logged in as PM	1. Click on newly created "Client Company" 2. Click on "New" 3. Click on "New Division" 4.Fill details 5.Click on "Create"	Divisions should be created successfully	Divisions are created successfully	PASS

TC_014	As a PM, I should be able to create Client admin for the client company	Logged in as PM	1.Navigate to newly created “Client Company” 2.Go to “People” tab 3.Click New 4.Fill details 5. Create	A person should get created for client company	User is successfully logged in	PASS
TC_015	As a PM, I should be able to assign role and valid credentials to client admin	Logged in as PM	1. Navigate to ”Security” tab 2.Enter password 3.Click on “Client Admin” role 4. Create	Person should be assigned “Client Admin” role	“Client Admin” role is assigned successfully	PASS
TC_016	As a PM, I should be able to logout from OHMS	Logged in as PM	1.Navigate to “Menu” 2.Click on “Sign-Out”	User should be logged-Out of OHMS successfully	User is successfully logged-Out	PASS
TC_017	As a PM, I should be able to revoke provider role from home company nurse	Logged in as PM	1. Navigate to “My Company” tab 2.Go to “People” tab. 3. Search for the nurse 4.Navigate to “Security” tab 5.Uncheck “Provider” role radio button 6. Save	Provider role should be revoked from the nurse successfully	Provider role is revoked successfully	PASS
TC_018	As a PM, I should be able to delete Nurses from home company	Logged in as PM	1. Navigate to “My Company” tab 2.Go to “People” tab. 3. Search for the nurse 4.Click “delete” tab 5.Delete	Nurse should be deleted successfully	Nurse is deleted successfully	PASS

TC_022	As a PM, I should be able to delete client admin from client company	Logged in as PM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to “client Company” tab 2. Search for the client company 3. Search for the client admin 4. Click “delete” tab 5. Delete 	client admin should be deleted successfully	client admin is deleted successfully	PASS
TC_023	As a PM, I should be able to delete employees of client company	Logged in as PM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to “client Company” tab 2. Search for the client company 3. Search for the Employee 4. Click “delete” tab 5. Delete 	Employee should be deleted successfully	Employee is deleted successfully	PASS
TC_024	As a PM, I should be able to delete client company Divisions	Logged in as PM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to “Client Company” tab 2. Search for the client company 3. Search for the Division 4. Click “delete” tab 5. Delete 	Division should be deleted successfully	Division is deleted successfully	PASS
TC_025	As a PM, I should be able to delete client company Sites	Logged in as PM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to “Client Company” tab 2. Search for the client company 3. Search for the Site 4. Click “delete” tab 5. Delete 	Site should be deleted successfully	Site is deleted successfully	PASS

TC_026	As an Admin, I should be able to revoke PM role	Logged in as Company Admin	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to "My Company" 2. Go to "People" tab. 3. Search for the PM 4. Navigate to "Security" tab 5. Uncheck "Program Manager" role radio button 6. Save 	"Program Manager" role should be revoked successfully	"Program Manager" role is revoked successfully	PASS
TC_027	As an Admin, I should be able to delete newly created program manager	Logged in as Admin	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to "My Company" tab 2. Go to "People" tab. 3. Search for the PM 4. Click "delete" tab 5. Delete 	PM should be deleted successfully	PM is deleted successfully	PASS

Table 1. Test cases for OHMS

3.2.3 Traceability Matrix

Traceability matrix is a critical part of testing as it ensures that the product delivered to the client is meeting all the stated requirements. Traceability matrix shows the mapping of the requirements with the test cases and ensures that all the critical requirements of the application have been covered by the test cases. It is a way to tie all the testing artifacts together from the starting to the end to ensure that the end product align with the goals and objectives of the project. The matrix in Table 2. shows the number of test cases which has been created in order to give full test coverage to the particular requirement.

One great benefit of this matrix is the ability to access the impact of any requirement change. When the requirement changes midway during the development of the software, this matrix helps the tester to track the number of test cases which has been affected by that particular requirement change.

Requirement ID	Requirement Description	Test Case ID	Status
RID_001	Login functionality of the OHMS	TC_001 TC_005	Pass
RID_002	Company Admin rights which involves :	TC_002 TC_003	Pass Pass
RID_003	Program Manager rights which involves :	TC_006 TC_007 TC_008 TC_011 TC_012 TC_013 TC_014 TC_015 TC_019 TC_020	Pass Pass Pass Pass Pass Pass Pass Pass Pass Pass
RID_004	Program manager rights	TC_009 TC_010 TC_017 TC_018	Pass Pass Pass Pass
RID_005	Logout functionality of the OHMS	TC_004 TC_016	Pass Pass

Figure 2. Traceability Matrix

3.2.4 Solution Structure for OHMS Project

Complete structure in which OHMS automation scripts have been managed inside Visual Studio is shown in Figure 3. All the test scripts are categorised on the basis of the type of action they are performing. The structure consists of three folders namely: Initialize Execution, Task Manager and Test Scripts. There is a separate section named as “Dependencies” which consist of all the selenium libraries and packages which have been installed in visual studio for carrying out the automation.

- **Initialize Execution:** It has the main class which helps to initialize the web driver by passing URL and credentials to Browser Start class.
- **Task Manager:** It has the base class which consists of two methods namely : Up method (for the creation of data) and Down method (for the deletion of created data). It need to be implemented by all the classes of “Test Script” folder.

- **Test Scripts:** This folder have the test scripts, which contains web elements, their xpath, selenium and C# commands for carrying out the execution on the OHMS.

Figure 3. Solution structure for OHMS Project

a) **Task Manager Folder**

This folder contains the Base class which has two abstract methods namely Up and Down under it. This base class is inherited, and methods are implemented by the classes of “Test Scripts” folder. Up method is used to create new entries in the OHMS and down method is used to delete the same entries at later stage.

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Text;

namespace OHMS.TaskManager
{
    public abstract class BaseClass
    {
        public abstract bool Up();
        public abstract bool Down();
    }
}
```

Figure 4. Task Manager

b) Initialize Execution folder

This folder contains the main class. This main class is the starting point of the execution and calls all other classes for performing different tasks. The first action performed by the main class is to pass driver name to the “browser start” class. Depending upon the passed parameter, “browser start” class will initialize the driver of the same browser and later will return the initialized driver back to the main class. Main class with the help of that driver will navigate to OHMS official site and later will call other test scripts to perform next actions. The code which has been used to create main class is shown in Figure 5.

```

public static void Main(string[] args)
{
    var successfullyCompletedTasks = new List<testTask>();
    var driver = BrowserStart.StartBrowser("Chrome", "OHMS website");
    int WAIT_TIME = 3000;
    string CompanyName = "New Company";
    string Male = "//input[@value='M']";
    string Female = "//input[@value='F']";
    string Site1 = "Headquarter";
    string Site2 = "Production";
    string Div1 = "Division1";
    string Div2 = "Division2";
    string Password = "XXXXXX";

    //Login as Admin
    Authenticate authenticateobjAdmin = new Authenticate(driver, "Admin", "XXXXX");
    Authenticate authenticatePMobj = null;
    CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompany CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompanyObj = null;
    AssigningRoleToHomeCompanyProgramManager assigningRoleobject = null;
    CreatingClientCompanyName CreatingClientCompanyNameobj = null;
    CreatingClientCompanySite CreatingClientCompanySiteobj = null;
    CreatingClientCompanySite CreatingClientCompanySite2obj = null;
    CreatingClientCompanyDiv CreatingClientCompanyDiv1obj = null;
    CreatingClientCompanyDiv CreatingClientCompanyDiv2obj = null;
    CreatingNurseForHomeCompany Nurse1ForHomeCompanyobj = null;
    CreatingNurseForHomeCompany Nurse2ForHomeCompanyobj = null;
    ProviderRoleToNurse ProviderRoleToNurse1obj = null;
    ProviderRoleToNurse ProviderRoleToNurse2obj = null;
    CreatingPeopleForClientCompany MaleEmployeeAucklandDiv1Obj = null;
    CreatingPeopleForClientCompany FemaleEmployeeAucklandDiv2Obj = null;
    CreatingPeopleForClientCompany MaleEmployeeWaikatoDiv1Obj = null;
    CreatingPeopleForClientCompany FemaleEmployeeWaikatoDiv2Obj = null;
    CreatingPeopleForClientCompany ClientAdminCreationObj = null;
    AssigningRoleToClientCompanyPeople AssigningAdminRoletoClientAdminObj = null;
    CreatingPeopleForClientCompany CompanyManagerCreationObj = null;
    AssigningRoletoClientCompanyPeople AssigningCompanyManagerRoleObj = null;

    if (authenticateobjAdmin.Up())
    {
        //creating home company person
        string Title = driver.Title;
        string AdminName = driver.FindElement(By.Id("uname")).Text;

        if (Title.Equals("Administration") && AdminName.Equals("Admin"))
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Login : Admin");
        else
            Console.WriteLine("Home page is not opened");
        CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompanyObj = new CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompany(driver, "PM", "HomeCompany",
            "PM@example.com");

        if (CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompanyObj.Up())
        {
            successfullyCompletedTasks.Add(testTask.CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompanyEnum);
            string PersonTitle = driver.Title;
            if (PersonTitle.Equals("Person"))
                Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Created : Home Company Person");
            else
                Console.WriteLine("Person is not created");

            //Assigning PM role
            assigningRoleobject = new AssigningRoleToHomeCompanyProgramManager(driver, "PM", "XXXXXX",
                "//div[@class='editor-field roletlist']/input[@value=5]");

            if (assigningRoleobject.Up())
            {
                string RoleTitle = driver.Title;
                if (RoleTitle.Equals("Details"))
                    Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Role Assigned : Program Manager for Home Company");
                else
                    Console.WriteLine("PM Role is not assigned");
                successfullyCompletedTasks.Add(testTask.AssigningRolesEnum);
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

//Logout as Admin
Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
driver.FindElement(By.Id("menulinkspan")).Click();
Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
driver.FindElement(By.XPath("//a[contains(.,'Sign Out')]")).Click();
Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Logout : Admin");
authenticatePMobj = new Authenticate(driver, "PM", "XXXXX");

if (authenticatePMobj.Up())
{
    successfullyCompletedTasks.Add(testTask.AuthenticatePMEnum);
    string ProgramManagerName = driver.FindElement(By.Id("uname")).Text;
    if (ProgramManagerName.Equals("PM HomeCompany"))
        Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Login : Program manager of Home Company");
    else
        Console.WriteLine("Home page is not opened");
    CreatingClientCompanyNameobj = new CreatingClientCompanyName(driver, CompanyName);

    if (CreatingClientCompanyNameobj.Up())
    {
        successfullyCompletedTasks.Add(testTask.CreatingClientCompanyNameEnum);
        string CompanyTitle = driver.Title;
        if (CompanyTitle.Equals("Details"))
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Client Company : Client company has been created");
        else
            Console.WriteLine("Company is not created");
        CreatingClientCompanySiteobj = new CreatingClientCompanySite(driver, Site1, "New Zealand:Auckland Region");

        if (CreatingClientCompanySiteobj.Up())
        {
            successfullyCompletedTasks.Add(testTask.CreatingClientCompanySiteEnum);
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Site 1 creation : Site has been created for client company");
            CreatingClientCompanySite2obj = new CreatingClientCompanySite(driver, Site2, "New Zealand:Waikato");
        }
    }
}

```

```

successfullyCompletedTasks.Reverse();
foreach (var task in successfullyCompletedTasks)
{
    switch (task)
    {
        case testTask.AuthenticatePMEnum:
            authenticatePMobj.Down();
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Logout : Program Manager");
            break;

        case testTask.CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompanyEnum:
            CreatingProgramManagerForHomeCompanyObj.Down();
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Person deletion : Person of Home Company successfully removed");
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Logout : Admin");
            break;

        case testTask.AssigningRolesEnum:
            assigningRoleobject.Down();
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Role removed : Program Manager role for Home Company person is" +
                " successfully revoked");
            break;

        case testTask.CreatingClientCompanyNameEnum:
            CreatingClientCompanyNameobj.Down();
            break;

        case testTask.CreatingClientCompanySiteEnum:
            CreatingClientCompanySiteobj.Down();
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Site 1 : Successfully removed");
            break;

        case testTask.CreatingClientCompanySite2Enum:
            CreatingClientCompanySite2obj.Down();
            Console.WriteLine("Test Case Passed : Site 2 : Successfully removed");
            break;
    }
}

```

Figure 5. Main class

c) Test Scripts Folder

This folder contains the test scripts which consist of all the web elements, their xpaths and the actions which are need to be performed on the OHMS. Each class under “Test Scripts” folder is named as per the task they are performing. Below is the brief explanation about the functionality of each script:

- **Brower Start:** Script to initialize the browser and to navigate to OHMS website.
- **Authenticate:** Script which will help the user to get logged-In to the OHMS and later to get logged-Out.
- **Creating Program Manager for Home Company:** Script to create a person for the home company and later to delete this person from the system.
- **Assigning Program Manager Role to Home Company person:** Script to assign Program Manager Role to the newly created person and to generate credentials and later to revoke the assigned role from the same person.
- **Creating Nurse for Home Company:** Script to create a Nurse for the home company and later to delete the nurse from the system.
- **Assigning Provider Role to Home Company Nurse:** Script to assign Provider role to the newly created nurse and to generate credentials and later to revoke the assigned role from the same person.
- **Creating Client Company:** Script to create client company.
- **Creating Client Company Sites:** Script to create sites for client company and later to remove these sites from the client company.
- **Creating Client Company Divisions:** Script to create divisions for client company and later to remove these divisions from the client company.
- **Creating People for Client Company:** Script to create employees,client admin and company manager for the client company and later to remove these people from the client company.
- **Assigning Roles to Client Company people:** Script to assign admin role and company manager role to the concerned people and later to revoke the assigned role from the same people.

d) Selected Tool

Below are few of the code snippets which have been created for OHMS using C# and selenium Webdriver. Appendices can be referred for the code snippets of all scripts.

Start browser class: It has implemented the three major drivers namely: Chrome, Firefox and IE. Depending on the user requirement, user passes a driver name from the main class. Once the driver name gets passed, the driver gets automatically initialized in the “Start Browser”. After initializing the driver, “Start Browser” returns the driver to the main class and now main class use this driver to execute the actions on the OHMS. The complete code for this class can be seen in Figure 6.

```

public class BrowserStart
{
    static IWebDriver driver;
    public static IWebDriver StartBrowser(String browsername, String URL)
    {
        if (browsername.Equals("Chrome"))
        {
            driver = new ChromeDriver(@"C:\Users\Anjali\.nuget\packages\selenium.webdriver.chromedriver\75.0.3770.140\driver\win32");
            //driver = new ChromeDriver();
        }

        else if (browsername.Equals("Firefox"))
        {
            driver = new ChromeDriver(@"C:\Users\Anjali\.nuget\packages\selenium.webdriver.chromedriver\75.0.3770.140\driver\win32");
            // System.setProperty("webdriver.gecko.driver", "C:\\Temp\\geckodriver.exe");
            driver = new FirefoxDriver();
        }
        else if (browsername.Equals("IE"))
        {
            driver = new ChromeDriver(@"C:\Users\Anjali\.nuget\packages\selenium.webdriver.chromedriver\75.0.3770.140\driver\win32");
            // System.setProperty("webdriver.ie.driver", "C:\\Temp\\IEDriverServer64bit.exe");
            driver = new InternetExplorerDriver();
        }
        driver.Navigate().GoToUrl(URL);
        driver.Manage().Window.Maximize();
        return driver;
    }
}

```

Figure 6. Start Browser Class

Authenticate Class: The test scripts which is created for the login credentials and then for logout is shown in Figure 7. The main class calls this authenticates class and at the same time passes the driver and the login credentials to this class. This class receives the parameters and at the same time inherited Base class so that it can implement the up and down methods. In up methods, the script is trying to login to the OHMS using valid login credentials and once all the entries are made, it finally logout from the OHMS using down method.

```

class Authenticate : BaseClass
{
    private IWebDriver driver;
    private static int WAIT_TIME = 3000;
    private string uid;
    private string pass;

    public Authenticate(IWebDriver Driver, string Uid, string Pass) {
        this.driver = Driver;
        this.uid = Uid;
        this.pass = Pass;
    }

    public override bool Up()
    {
        driver.FindElement(By.Id("UserName")).SendKeys(uid);
        driver.FindElement(By.Id("Password")).SendKeys(pass);
        driver.FindElement(By.Id("LoginButton")).Click();
        Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
        return true;
    }

    public override bool Down()
    {
        Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
        driver.FindElement(By.Id("menulinkspan")).Click();
        Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
        driver.FindElement(By.XPath("//a[contains(., 'Sign Out')]")).Click();
        Thread.Sleep(WAIT_TIME);
        Authenticate authenticateobj = new Authenticate(driver, "XXXX@gmail.com", "XXXX");
        return true;
    }
}

```

Figure 7. Authenticate class

4. RESULTS

The results of the test scripts execution are shown in Figure 8. The snippet shows what all test scripts has been executed along with their execution result. The first half of the results have covered the scenarios related to login as an Admin in the OHMS, creating PM followed by creation of the client company and employees for that company and then assigning different roles to these people according to their profile.

The second half of the result is about revoking the different roles assigned to the people, deleting the created entries and finally getting logged-Out from the OHMS. Deletion of these entries was critical for this project as Company had limited database storage. And also, earlier these entries were getting deleted manually by the database admin which was again a time consuming activity. Hence by automating the deletion process, testing team has saved a lot of effort and time.

```

C:\Program Files\dotnet\dotnet.exe
Test Case Passed : Login as Erudite Admin
Test Case Passed : Create a Home Company Person
Test Case Passed : Role Assigned : Program Manager for Home Company
Test Case Passed : Logout : Erudite Admin
Test Case Passed : Login as Program manager of Home Company
Test Case Passed : Client Company : Client company has been created
Test Case Passed : Site 1 creation : Site has been created for client company
Test Case Passed : Site 2 creation : Site has been created for client company
Test Case Passed : Division 1 creation : Division has been created for client company
Test Case Passed : Division 2 creation : Division has been created for client company
Test Case Passed : Nurse 1 creation : Nurse 1 has been created for home company
Test Case Passed : Provide role given : Nurse 1 has been given provider role for home company
Test Case Passed : Nurse 2 creation : Nurse 2 has been created for home company
Test Case Passed : Provide role given : Nurse 2 has been given provider role for home company
Test Case Passed : Male Employee Auckland site creation : Employee has been created for Div 1 in Auckland Site
Test Case Passed : Female Employee Auckland site creation : Employee has been created for Div 2 in Auckland Site
Test Case Passed : Male Employee Waikato site creation : Employee has been created for Div 1 in Waikato Site
Test Case Passed : Female Employee Waikato site creation : Employee has been created for Div 2 in Waikato Site
Test Case Passed : Person created for client Admin
Test Case Passed : Client Admin Role Assigned to client company person
Test Case Passed : Person created for company manager
Test Case Passed : Company manager Role Assigned to client company person
Test Case Passed : Company Manager role from the person of Home company has been successfully revoked
Test Case Passed : Person for the role of Company Manager is successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Person for the role of Client Admin is successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Client Admin role from the person of Home company has been successfully revoked
Test Case Passed : Waikato Female employee successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Waikato Male employee successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Auckland Female employee successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Auckland Male employee successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Provider role from Nurse 2 is successfully revoked
Test Case Passed : Nurse 2 is successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Provider role from Nurse 1 is successfully revoked
Test Case Passed : Nurse 1 is successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Division 2 : Successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Division 1 : Successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Site 2 : Successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Site 1 : Successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Company name cannot be deleted
Test Case Passed : Logout : Program Manager
Test Case Passed : Login : Erudite Admin
Test Case Passed : Role removed : Program Manager role for Home Company person is successfully revoked
Test Case Passed : Person deletion : Person of Home Company successfully removed
Test Case Passed : Logout : Erudite Admin

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Figure 8. Test script execution result for OHMS

5. DISCUSSION

This paper main focus was to create automation test scripts for OHMS based on the client requirements and later to create a suite which will be used for regression testing later. Creation of automation regression suit is accomplished by using Visual studio and selenium Webdriver with C# programming language.

The major issue Company was facing was the amount of manual efforts which were used to test the whole application manually again and again whenever a change is introduced to the application. These midway changes were getting introduces because of various reasons which includes change in client requirement, defect fix or feature enhancements. Another bug challenge for the company was the need of physically going to client location to validate the correct installation of OHMS in client premises. Research papers and the requirements of this project helped to determine the need of going for regression automation testing. Moreover, budget constraint for OHMS suggested the team to go for the open source tools. These are not only free but also have a huge community support.

Due to involvement of diverse clients, the company was not having a clear definition of the requirements therefore it was practically impossible to make an estimation of the time and costs that would be involved in this project. As a result, this paper suggested adopting scrum methodology. It is flexible and adaptable in nature. In addition to this, Client feel more involved as they have the option to see a project's progress throughout its lifespan—not, giving them an opportunity to collaborate and watch the project move from start to finish. In addition to this there are many research papers which support the use of Scrum methodology for a successful delivery of a product.

There were few issues which were faced during this research. One of them was having limited amount of database for OHMS. As a result, it was important to delete the data whenever a new entry is made in OHMS. Another issue was the data which was getting entered into the application was getting linked to the other database following primary-foreign key concept. Hence it was impossible to delete the primary keys without first deleting the linked foreign keys. To resolve the above mentioned issues, this paper suggested the idea of creating a deleting mechanism as well for the scripts. So, for every entry which has been made in the application there was a connected delete mechanism and hence the need of up and down method came into the picture.

One more issue which was found during the research was related to the web elements. Web elements are the critical part for any web automation testing. These are the interactive elements on which the action is actually performed. There were few web elements available in the application that were not assigned unique id or name and were changing the values dynamically which made their detection quite difficult. To overcome this problem, it was decided that testing team need to make a list of all these types of web elements and need to ask developers to assign unique ids. In places where giving unique ids were not possible, relative Xpath have been used.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the issues which were faced during this research, below are the few recommendations:

- Introducing automation testing in the early phase of software development is not advised. Automation tested should only be approached once the critical functionalities or features of the application have been stable and freed. OHMS is still in its early development

phase and new features are still getting added to this application. Continuous change in these critical functionalities will require rework in the automation scripts, affecting the time and effort of the testers.

- Before going for the automation testing, product should be thoroughly tested manually. At time absence of manual testing or investing less time in manual testing adversely affect the time required for automation testing. The same issue was faced while automating OHMS. Many a time while creating scripts, there were few critical bugs which were found. As a result, creating scripts for those particular functionalities was getting on hold until the issue is fixed hence impacting the time frame which has been assigned for automation.
- It is also recommended to use framework like TestNG for easy maintenance of test scripts and for reporting purpose. Currently console output has been used to reflect the test script execution results. TestNG is very helpful for unit testing, it upholds parallel testing and group testing, and gives a user-friendly reporting experience.
- It is also recommended to use defect reporting and tracking tool. A bug tracking tool not only helps in reporting and tracking of bugs but also ensures that the flaws are removed and bugs are fixed. It helps the testing team to recognize the repetitive issues and come up with a permanent solution. Since bug tracking software helps to segregate high and low priority issues, development team can focus on the high priority stuff, instead of wasting time on the minor issues.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper focuses on creation of automated regression suite for OHMS using open source tools. This paper have tried to help the company in overcoming its two main problems which include too much of manual efforts in the execution of same test cases again and again and the time and cost required to validate the correct installation of the software in client premises. The frequency of OHMS builds to meet frequently changed requirements mean that certain tests must be run over and over again to ensure that changes to software applications have not impacted the integrity of OHMS. Automated Regression suite will verify that existing software performs correctly even after it has been updated. By creating automation regression suite, now team can validate if the application is working fine with just one click and can execute the suite as many time as needed to check the critical functionality of the application. It also helped the team to ensure if any major or minor changes which has been made at later stages due to client requirement has impacted the critical functionality of the application. This report has also highlighted few issues which have been faced during the testing and the alternatives taken by the team to tackle these bottlenecks. For issues related to the database constraints, testing team came up with the idea of creating deleting mechanism, which would run automatically once all the entries have been created. The current research will provide guidelines to the future researchers on how to create an automated regression suite for any web application with the help of open source tools namely Visual Studio, Selenium Web driver and Trello.

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AUTHORS

I am Anjali Rawat, QA lead in Born Digital, New Zealand. Before this I was working with Wipro Limited, India as a Test Analyse where I get an opportunity to work with clients like Vodafone, Cisco and Bharti Airtel. I had experience in Networking, database testing, regression testing, manual testing and automation testing. I am passionate about testing and love to deliver quality product to the customers.

Dr. Shahid Ali is a senior lecturer and IT program leader at AGI Education Limited, Auckland, New Zealand. He has published number of research papers on ensemble learning. His expertise and research interests include ensemble learning, machine learning, data mining and knowledge discovery.